

PROJECT

Agroecological Production of Sweet Acorn

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Historical Value and Identity

Acorn is the fruit of the oaks, and the most used for consumption in Alentejo (Portugal) is the one from the native holm oak (*Quercus rotundifolia*), which is the sweetest.

Until the 20th century, acorn was an important part of the human diet in Portugal, but due to changes in rural population lifestyle and growing urbanisation, acorns consumption dropped abruptly. Since then, it has been used mostly for feed.

This product is slowly being re-introduced as niche activity by some agri-food companies. The products made with acorn represent a way to keep tradition alive and support sustainable systems (Fonseca, 2020).

Bolota (acorn) harvest - Freixo do Meio, Winter 2021

Montado in Freixo do Meio Farm

Montado is an agro-silvo-pastoral system, recognized as a semi-natural extensive habitat, which is distributed mostly in southern Portugal and Spain and composed mainly by the native tree species of holm oaks (*Quercus rotundifolia*) and cork oaks (*Quercus suber*), natural pastures and shrubs. Montado is the most common habitat in **Freixo do Meio** farm, covering ca. 450 ha.

Montado Landscape - Freixo do Meio, Spring 2020

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Freixo do Meio is valorising acorns in food industry since 2007. Actually, around 14 different products are currently commercialized, such as flour, bread, infusion, burgers and sausages and spreads.

Nutritional Value

Acorns composition depends on many factors, such as genetic variability, climatic conditions or soil composition. Nonetheless, it is known that, generally, they have high content in phytochemical compounds, which are responsible for their antioxidant, anticarcinogenic and cardioprotective properties. They are mainly composed by carbohydrates, especially starch, with significant amounts of lipids and low protein content (see Table 1). According to Vinha et. al (2016), acorns have a higher nutritional value than cereals, being more rich in fibre, fat and complex carbohydrates. The fact that they are gluten-free, makes them an excellent option for celiac people.

Table 1. Comparison of the nutritional value between acorn flour (from holm oak) and wheat flour (Silva et. al, 2016).

Nutritional Value (100g)	ACORN FLOUR	WHEAT FLOUR
Carbohydrates (%)	75.22 – 84.09	70
Starch (%)	51.79 – 58	60 – 75
Protein (%)	4.32 – 5	10 – 18
Fat (%)	8.44 – 13.86	1.34
Fiber (%)	10.89 – 17.9	1.9
Gluten (%)	—	36

RADIANT Project

Through the principles of agroecology and aiming at the economic development of the sweet acorn, **Freixo do Meio** will:

- Identify and map at local and regional level, sweet acorns trees (interviewing neighbours and traditional collectors),
- Select sweet acorns to multiply with a Matrix of Acceptability Criteria (interviewing regional and local actors),
- Promote vegetative reproduction of the selected trees (supported by oak grafting experts),
- Implement an Agroecological Orchard on the farm,
- Monitor, adapt and improve the associated agroecological practices.

References

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